

THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURAL TOURISM COMMUNITY ENTERPRISES AND FARMER MAID NETWORKS TO HAVE THE CAPACITY TO DEVELOP HUMAN RESOURCES TO ENHANCE THE COMMUNITY ECONOMY ACCORDING TO THE KING'S PHILOSOPHY, SAMUT SONGKHRAM PROVINCE

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Abstract

The objectives of this research are: 1) To study the condition and problems of the implementation of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks, Samut War province to manage the human resource development of agricultural tourism community enterprises 2) To study the innovative elements of the development of community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province 3) To develop community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province. The population in this research was divided into 3 groups: the first group was a specific sample of volunteers, divided into 3 groups of 30 people. The second group is a member of the Agricultural Tourism Community Enterprises, Samut Songkhram Province, 250 people and the third group is a group of luminaries, 5 people. Using research tools, interviews and questionnaires, the IOC averaged 0.81 with a confidence value of .93 rather than 0.80. Data analysis uses exploratory component analysis, statistics, percentages, averages, standard deviations, and content analysis. The study found that 1) conditions and operational problems showed that there was no encouragement for personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises to develop their potential by participating in market activities, creating and developing traditional market activities in the community economy, online marketing versus offline marketing, and seeking market management approaches in the community economy according to King's Philosophy 2) The exploratory elements of innovation have a total of 4 elements and 25 component attributes And 3) Innovation development There are 4 processes: the 1st process on promoting knowledge according to the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, the 2nd process on promoting the organization according to the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, the 3rd process on promoting the competency of personnel in the profession according to the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, and the 4th process on promoting the management of information technology according to the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy. The results of the satisfaction assessment of innovative developments in training for marketers, enterprises, Agri-tourism communities and the Network of Farmers' Housewives, according to King's Philosophy, Samut War province, had the highest overall average satisfaction.

Keywords: Human Resource Development / Community Enterprises / the King's Philosophy

INTRODUCTION

The government has formulated a 20-year Thailand development strategy during 2017-2037. Under the concept of Thailand 4.0 or Thailand 4.0, community tourism and creative products, environmental and cultural conservation to promote creative production and empower local and community tourism, and competitive, stable and sustainable tourism. This is achieved in line with the country's goal of enabling Thailand to manage the high-value-added tourism chain in the global market and strengthen communities and society. As well as being a tourism owner who is critical to Thailand's economic and social development towards vision, stability, prosperity and sustainability (Ministry of Tourism and Sports, 2014: 1).

For the above reasons, it is of interest to contribute to the development of the new generation of agricultural-minded people to know how to manage agriculture through innovation and modern technology, be creative, and be able to expand into entrepreneurship, self-reliance and local agricultural leadership. In the early stages, farmers would center and design self-learning (Suddhanom Tanchaen, 2016:1-3). This includes the implementation of research findings to propose ways to drive policy pushing innovation, learning networks to promote and develop agricultural tourism community enterprises to further strengthen community solidarity. This is because community solidarity is important and is one of the indicators that will make community tourism, sustainable (Khanidda Kraisanti and Rasmant Khamsri, 2016). It is also one of the elements that create the power to drive community development in all dimensions because it enables collaboration to help each other achieve the goals set by the community and gives rise to the power to move the community in the desired direction. As a result of sustainable community development, the panel recognized the importance of promoting community enterprises and developing community products. By studying the needs of executives and members of community enterprises, coupled with the needs of tourists in line with the government's policy of promoting tourism, the main cities, secondary cities, for economic and social development at the local level has clearly created a model for promoting agriculture. To develop good quality production, to develop quality production activities in accordance with the community way, and to create marketing. Community-based agricultural products have a king-based approach to sustainability.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

- 1) To study the condition and problems of the implementation of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks, Samut War province to manage the human resource development of agricultural tourism community enterprises.
- 2) To study the innovative elements of the development of community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province.

3) To develop community enterprises, agricultural tourism and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Findings

The results of the study, conditions and problems of implementation of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' maid networks, Samut War province in the management of human resource development of agricultural tourism community enterprises.

Conditions and operational problems It were found that there is no encouragement for personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises to develop their potential by participating in market activities, creating and developing traditional market activities in the community economy, online marketing and offline marketing, and seeking market management approaches in the community economy trajectory according to King's Philosophy.

The results of the analysis of the innovative elements of the learning network towards the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and the farmers' network to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province.

Table 1: Data suitability checks

Questionnaire	Number of Questions (Variables)	KMO	Bartlett's Test Sphericity		
			Approx. Chi-square	df	Sig.
Human Resource Development	25	.921	4875.565	300	.000

According to Table 1, the results of the data analysis analyzed the exploratory elements of learning network innovation towards the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to King's Philosophy, Samut War province. When examining the preliminary agreement, it was found that the correlation matrix of the 25 variables is not an identity matrix, that is, the 25 variables are sufficiently correlated to be able to continue the analysis of the elements (Bartlett's Test of Sphericity Approx. Chi-Square = 4875.565, df = 300, Sig. = .000) (Kalya Vanishay, 2013). When considering the individual variables, the overall sample selection adequacy (MSA) value is equal to .921, and the range of sample selection sufficiency (MSA) of the 25 variables is 0.99-0.90, which is greater than every 0.5. This indicates that all the variables studied have sufficient correlations to be used for analysis.

Table 2: Statistical values after element extraction

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% Of Variance	Cumulative %
1	12.092	48.367	48.367	12.092	48.367	48.367	5.432	21.726	21.726
2	2.212	8.848	57.216	2.212	8.848	57.216	5.011	20.044	41.771
3	1.388	5.553	62.769	1.388	5.553	62.769	4.262	17.048	58.819
4	1.072	4.287	67.055	1.072	4.287	67.055	2.059	8.237	67.055
5	.929	3.716	70.771						
6	.809	3.237	74.008						
...									
25	.098	.392	100.000						

According to Table 2, the results of the analysis of the elements of the innovation variables of the learning network to promote and develop agricultural tourism community enterprises and the farmers' network to develop human resources to enhance the community economy, according to The King's Philosophy, Samut War province, showed that a total of 25 variables were studied, it can create 4 important elements. It considers a number of elements of Eigenvalues greater than 1.00 according to Kaiser's law, and can explain the variations in all 25 variables in 67.055 percent. The results of the analysis of the elements when the axis is rotated by the varimax method. It was found that element 1 described variance of 21.726 percent, element 2 described variance of 41.771 percent, and element 3 described variance of 58.819 percent. The optimal number of elements is determined by the sequence in which the elements of the actual data with Eigenvalues are higher than the sequence of elements that the program simulates, resulting in the results of the analysis. 4 The researchers collected the data with exploratory factor analysis (EFA) of innovative learning networks towards the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy and the attributes of the 25 variable elements, element 1 has 7 variables with element weight values greater than .20 with element weight values between 0.847 and 0.525, element 2 has 10 variables with element weight values greater than .20 with element weight values between 0.745 and 0.476, element 3 has 5 variables with element weight values greater than .20, with element weight values between 0.755 and 0.534, and element 4 has 3 variables with element weight values greater than .20 with element weight values between 0.749 and 0.655.

The results of the synthesis of data are then used to integrate the learning network innovations into the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy, according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province, with details of the results of the study and analysis of the basic data in each section, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Innovation of learning networks towards the promotion and development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmers' networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province

There are 4 components and 25 methods of promoting human resource development capacity	Promoting knowledge in the community economy according to The King's Philosophy
	Promoting community economic organizations based on The King's Philosophy
	Promoting the competency of personnel in the profession in accordance with the community economic trajectory according to The King's Philosophy
	Promoting information technology management in the direction of community economy according to The King's Philosophy

The result of the development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmer maid networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province.

There are 4 processes and 25 methods that can start from any previous stage: the 1st process on promoting knowledge along the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, the 2nd process on promoting the organization according to the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, the 3rd process on promoting the competency of personnel in the profession according to the community economy according to the King's Philosophy, and the 4th process on promoting the management of information technology according to the community economy according to the King's Philosophy. Satisfactory assessment of innovative development by key contributors of the 250 students trained in the Marketers Course, community enterprises, agricultural tourism and the Network of Farmers' Housewives according to The King's Philosophy, the Samut War province had the highest overall satisfaction level.

DISCUSSION

The result of the development of agricultural tourism community enterprises and farmer maid networks to have the capacity to develop human resources to enhance the community economy according to The King's Philosophy, Samut Songkhram Province, has 4 processes: The first process for promoting knowledge according to the community economy, according to King's Philosophy, i.e. The development of learning processes resulting from study visits. The transfer of knowledge of community sages and luminaries includes the exchange of learning to generate income. Create careers to strengthen community enterprises and farmers' networks. The second process for promoting the organization is based on the community economic trajectory according to King's Philosophy, namely, developing the leadership skills of the thought organization, the skills of working with community enterprises and the farmers' housewife network to produce and develop the agricultural products and services of community enterprises and the farmers' housewife network better under the principles of the King's Philosophy. The third process of promoting the competence of personnel in the profession

according to the community economic trajectory according to King's Philosophy is the condition in which the personnel in the community enterprises and the farmers' housewives network have the love, faith and pride of being community enterprise operators and the farmers' housewives network have attributes such as honesty, patience, courage to change, creative initiative and the ability to manage marketing and sales, strategic management, as well as embrace the King's Philosophy in living and working. And the fourth process for promoting information technology management in accordance with the community economic trajectory according to The King's Philosophy is the management of agricultural crop production through the use of information technology for research, as well as marketing channels to promote market management and agricultural products and services of community enterprises and farmers' networks. They have knowledge and understanding of all stages of work, including work development, product development and problem solving of work problems for community enterprises and farmers' networks, building trust in the network's collaboration to achieve quality agricultural products and services that meet consumer acceptance standards. In line with Wutthichai Limorunothai (2019) has studied human resource management models for sustainable organizational development, case studies of small and medium-sized enterprises in Bangkok and its vicinity in the current conditions where the environment is changing rapidly, technology is advanced and constantly evolving. Managing the organization's work to meet the needs of consumers in order to gain a competitive advantage requires a human resource management approach and an organizational development approach to be in line with the constantly changing situation in order to bring the organization into a balance between the economy, society and environment, leading to the sustainability of the organization. The findings from the examination of structural relationship models for path analysis showed that human resource management, consisting of talent management, good people management, and happiness management, affects organizational development and affects the sustainability of the organization. And in line with Swanson & Holton III (2009), it says that the core elements of human resource development are associated with learning development activities, the development of performance at both the individual and organizational levels, as well as the development of the organization as a whole. Human resource development processes in the organization.

SUGGESTION

1. In terms of knowledge promotion along the lines of community-based economic trajectory should encourage community enterprises to encourage personnel in community enterprises to learn farming together with model farmers and community sages to develop knowledge, understanding and motivation to pursue agricultural careers. Community enterprises, encourage personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises to participate in studies from agricultural prototypes to be applied to generate income from the production and distribution of their own agricultural produce.
2. In terms of promoting the organization in accordance with the science-based community economic trajectory, it should allow agricultural tourism community enterprises to have personnel who can be guided or lecturers within the tourist destinations who have the

knowledge and ability to provide information on agricultural tourism. Community enterprises of the conference to determine the aims. Role in creating businesses in the performance of tasks according to the competence and aptitude of personnel in agricultural tourism community enterprises in the community economy according to King's Philosophy.

3. In terms of promoting the competence of personnel in the profession in accordance with the community economic trajectory according to the King's Philosophy, the agricultural tourism community enterprises should be able to transfer knowledge through the local wisdom of the community. The Agri-tourism community enterprises of having personnel who serve with a smile, cheeky, polite and welcoming friendly and warm welcome familiar to tourists.

4. In terms of promoting information technology management in accordance with the community economy, according to the King's Philosophy, community enterprises should encourage the creation of new jobs. From the use of information technology in the community economy, according to King's Philosophy.

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